

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGES ON HUMAN HEALTH AND PSYCHOLOGY, POSSIBILITIES AND WAYS OF ELIMINATING THE PROBLEMS

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Abstract

In the article, the consequences caused by climate change and the ways to eliminate the problem are examined in detail. The necessity of implementing various measures to eliminate the problems caused by climate changes at both the global and local level is also brought into consideration in the article. The directions of the conducted and necessary measures have been determined. For example, attention was paid to the necessity of climate change prevention (mitigation), adaptation (adaptation) and changing individual and social behaviors for healthy living of societies. In the article, the fact that climate changes are related to the increase in temperature and weather conditions in the world as a result of global warming, and the fact that wars create an ecological crisis are also touched upon. Against the background of these changes, many environmental, economic and social problems arose, the tasks ahead were involved in research, and these problems required the joint efforts of different countries in the world. Measures such as switching to alternative energy sources, environmental protection and reducing carbon emissions are important to address these issues. In order to overcome the problems caused by climate change, archaeological etc. in areas rich in natural resources. there is also a need to strengthen state control over excavation works. We all have an individual, local and global responsibility to prevent climate change and combat the challenges it creates. Taking action without delay is essential to ensure the well-being of future generations.

Climate changes have serious effects on human health and psychology. Extreme weather events, droughts, floods and other climate changes have a negative impact on people's physical and psychological health. [Haines et al., 2006; Patz et al., 2005]. All these create negative traumas in people's lives and activities. As a result of the effects of climate changes, physical health effects, that is, extreme weather events, especially heat waves, can cause cardiovascular diseases and other health problems in humans [Kovats et al., 2003]. Extreme climate changes also affect people's psychological health. For example, the incidence of climate anxiety, stress, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) among humans has increased in recent years [Cunsolo Willocks et al., 2013]. Heat waves caused by climate change increase the risk of people suffering from cardiovascular diseases [Kovats et al., 2003]. Especially elderly and weak population groups are more exposed to these effects. In addition, disasters such as extreme weather events, droughts, and floods cause physical health injuries and deaths [Patz et al., 2005]. Extreme weather events associated with climate change, such as droughts, floods and heat waves, seriously threaten human health. Drought can lead to reduced water resources, reduced food productivity, and consequent food shortages. Flooding also accelerates the spread of disease, as the risk of infectious diseases increases as a result of water pollution. Heat waves can cause cardiovascular disease, heat stroke and even death. Especially the elderly and children are more sensitive to these effects. Climate change also facilitates the spread of vector-borne diseases. For example, mosquito-borne diseases such as

malaria and dengue fever spread over wider geographies. The spread of these diseases has a negative impact on people's health, especially in tropical and subtropical regions. Deterioration of water quality and reduced water supply can also lead to an increase in water-borne diseases (eg diarrhoea, typhus). In recent years, a phenomenon known as "climate anxiety" (eco-anxiety) has developed among psychologists. People are worried about the dangers of climate change and the uncertain future. Younger generations in particular feel the weight of facing the environmental challenges caused by climate change, which has a negative impact on their mental health. This anxiety and stress creates serious concerns about how they will cope with the effects of climate change in the future. The impact of climate change on human health and psychology is a serious issue, and these impacts manifest themselves in various directions. In order to prevent these problems, both physical and psychological measures should be taken. The development of health infrastructure and the creation of large-scale psychological support programs can greatly support people in coping with these changes [Haines et al., 2006; WHO, 2015]. People losing their homes, being displaced, and experiencing a lack of resources as a result of extreme weather events lead to traumatic experiences.

As a result of floods, hurricanes and fires, people suffer not only physical losses, but also serious emotional and psychological blows. For example, depression and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) are more common among homeless people. Adaptation strategies play a key role in combating climate change.

People and governments must take action to adapt to these challenges. Adaptation measures include various activities:

- **Strengthening health infrastructure:** Health systems need to be strengthened to combat climate-related diseases. To reduce the spread of infectious diseases, vaccines, medical equipment and emergency systems must be improved.

- **Early warning systems:** Early warning systems should be established against extreme weather events. These systems will help people take precautions before events such as floods, hurricanes and heat waves.

- **Psychological support programs** are essential to reduce the effects of environmental traumas and climate anxiety. The organization of rehabilitation programs for people who are forcibly displaced as a result of climate change or who have experienced traumatic experiences is also an important condition. This includes various services:

- **Counseling services:** Strengthening psychological counseling services will help to overcome psychological problems caused by climate change. Counselors can play a big role in the fight against stress, anxiety and depression.

- **Community-based support groups:** Support groups can be organized in local communities to deal with climate change stress. These groups allow people to share their feelings about climate change and support each other.

Informing and educating people about climate change is a necessity today. It is also necessary for the public to be aware and take the right measures to combat climate change. Educational programs, media campaigns, various actions can be added here. In this regard, educational programs on the effects of climate change should be organized in schools and universities, through which young people should be taught how to deal with environmental problems.

Information about the effects of climate change on health and psychology by the mass media can also increase awareness among the population. As the media raises people's awareness of this issue, their problem-solving skills should also be developed. Health infrastructure must be strengthened to combat climate change (WHO, 2015). Psychological support services and counseling programs are important for maintaining people's psychological health (González et al., 2016).

A clearer explanation of the effects of climate change on human health and psychology and the ways to eliminate these effects is given in table 1:

Table 1.

In addition to showing the effects of climate change on human health and psychology, the table also clarifies the ways to eliminate these effects.

Area of Influence	Impacts of Climate Change Ways to Eliminate Problems	Impacts of Climate Change Ways to Eliminate Problems
Physical Health	Extreme heat waves, drought, floods, vector-borne diseases	Health infrastructure strengthening, early warning systems
Psychological Health	Climate anxiety, trauma, forced displacement	Psychological support programs, counseling services, community-based support groups
Spread of Diseases	Malaria, waterborne diseases	Increasing vaccinations and medical supplies, improving sanitation and water quality
Environmental Traumas	Homelessness due to extreme weather events, lack of natural resources	Rehabilitation programs for displaced persons, social support systems

The effects of current climate changes on human health and psychology, as well as the ways to eliminate these effects, can be different. It depends both on the region, the climate, and the aspect of the country's and society's view of this problem. Effective, workable strategies must be developed to address the impact of

climate change on human health and psychology. It is important to take certain measures to reduce the serious effects of climate change on human health and psychology.

It is known that extreme weather events and the spread of various new and serious diseases have a negative impact on human physical health. In recent years, severe natural disasters and the consequences of wars have created serious pathologies in human health and psychology. Climate anxiety and traumas lead to psychological problems. Adaptation strategies, psychological support programs and awareness campaigns are of great importance to overcome these problems. The joint efforts of individuals, communities and governments are essential to effectively combat climate change. The situation in the Middle East, where forced displacement is rampant, in our world, where other hotbeds of war are combined with climate change, it is possible to eliminate the problems that have reached the point of disaster thanks to the joint cooperation and humanity of societies. Climate changes are related to the increase in temperature and changes in weather conditions around the world as a result of global warming. These changes create many environmental, economic and social problems. These problems require the joint efforts of different countries in the world. Measures such as switching to alternative energy sources, environmental protection and reducing carbon emissions are important to address these issues. In order to overcome the problems caused by climate change, various measures are being implemented at both global and local levels. These measures are mainly divided into three directions: prevention of climate changes (mitigation), adaptation (adaptation) and changing individual and social behaviors.

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